

Gesture based synthesis of bowed string instruments

by

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Submitted in partial fulfilment of the requirements for
the degree of Diploma of Advanced Studies.
Doctorate in Computer Science and Digital Communication
Department of Technology

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Universitat Pompeu Fabra

Barcelona, 4th August 2006

Abstract

Synthesis of traditional music instruments has been an active research area and there exist successful implementations of instruments with low degree of control like non-sustained excitation instruments. But for instruments with sustained excitation, such as bowed strings or wind instruments, where the interaction between instrument and performer is continuous, the quality of existing models is far from realistic.

In general, musical instrument synthesis techniques try to model the instrument but forget about the interaction between performer and instrument, that is musically much more relevant than the instrument itself. This interaction covers expressivity, the intentional nuances and gestures that make the performer, but also what we call naturalness, that is, non intentional gestures made by the performer due to the physical constraints of the instrument, the playing technique, etc. These non-intentional gestures give a specific flavor to the sound of the performance, that make it sound natural and realistic.

We can roughly classify the existing synthesis techniques into two categories: Physical models that focus on physical phenomena of sound production, and spectral models that focus on sound perception. With physical models naturalness and expressivity can hardly be reached without the need of controlling a huge amount of parameters that require the instrument itself, as well as a mastery comparable with the traditional performer and spectral models lack of performer interaction and articulation, that is, gestures.

The aim of this work is to try to improve the quality in instrument sound synthesis, specifically for the violin family. We propose a hybrid model combining spectral and physical models to take advantage of the characteristics of both approaches, focusing on the gestures of the performer with the objective to provide naturalness in the synthesis.

Acknowledgements

I would like to thank everyone from the Music Technology Group, specially Dr. Xavier Serra, my supervisor, Enric Guaus and Jordi Bonada for their involvement and help in the development of this research.

Further thanks to my colleagues Hugo Solis, Maarten Grachten, Esteban Maestre, Amaury Hazan and Dr. Rafael Ramirez, for their day to day feedback and to Guillermo Navarro for the violin performances.

This research was funded by a scholarship from Universitat Pompeu Fabra and from the EU-IST European Project *Sound to Sense, Sense to Sound* (*S2S²*)

Finally, I would like to thank all my friends and my family, and above all, special thanks go to Kristin Baumann for her support and encouragement.

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Chapter 1

Introduction

“As a musical instrument, the computer has unlimited potentialities for uttering sound. It can, in fact, produce strings of numbers representing any conceivable or hearable sound... Wonderful things would come out of that box if only we knew how to evoke them.”

[From John R. Pierce, 1965: “Portrait of the Computer as a Young Artist” [39]]

1.1 Digital sound synthesis

Digital sound synthesis has been a very active research area during the past years, since the introduction of computers. See [11] for an overview of the last 40 years research in computer music.

Computers, as a general-purpose machine have infinite possibilities for producing sound and computer music appears to be very promising compared to music production until now, that is limited by physical and technical constraints. Research in digital sound synthesis aims at providing models and tools to feed the computer and get “that wonderful thing” out of it.

Digital sound synthesis allows widening of the boundaries of timbre, perception, and performance techniques. A new wider space full of possibilities. It is a multidisciplinary field where scientists, composers, engineers and performers are developing together a new musical medium.

1.1.1 Imitative sound production

Imitative production of sounds is an old task. From very old traditions where sounds of the nature are imitated, to synthesizers imitating other instruments [11]. This work is about imitating the sound of the violin instrument family, inside this new musical medium. But, why imitate an existing instrument? Should not we navigate through this new space and propose new experiences instead? The question is that even provided with

such powerful tools, to which extent are we able to control them? Are we able to imitate the existing acoustic instruments? Understanding of traditional instruments is fundamental and will lead to better development of the models that will feed our magic box. Apart from this challenge, the wide range of applications, and the fact that realistic synthesis of traditional instruments will be an important economical factor for the industry, is more than enough to justify the effort being done in instrument sound imitation.

1.2 The performer-instrument interaction

A bad quality violin played by a top violin player, would sound better than a Stradivarius in the hands of a pianist.

With this sentence we want to emphasize the importance of the interaction and control in a music performance.

Most of the existing models that imitate traditional musical instruments, are models of instruments with a low degree of interaction, generally instruments that are impulsively excited, such as the piano, guitar, etc. But in the case of sustained excitation instruments such as bowed string instruments and wind instruments, where the degree of interaction with the performer is much bigger, high quality models are still missing.

One of the main problems in existing instrument sound synthesis techniques is that in general they model the instrument, or the sound produced by the instrument (from a physical or an acoustical analysis), but they ignore the interaction between performer and instrument. In this interaction several factors play an important role: the physical constraints of the instrument and performer, the skill of the performer, expressivity, tempo and microtiming, articulation, phrasing and all sort of nuances. It is the most important feature in a performance, and thus, we have to take it into account if we intend to obtain realistic and musically acceptable performances.

1.2.1 Controls, actions and gestures

A musical instrument as a physical interface, has a set of controls that is handled by the performer through physical actions.

Musical gesture is a very complex and highly interdisciplinary topic that can be approached from very different perspectives. In [1] we find a useful categorization of musical gestures into three groups, defined as follows:

- Sound-producing gestures, such as hitting, stroking, bowing, blowing, singing, kicking, etc. and mental images of those gestures.
- Sound-accompanying gestures, including all kinds of movements we can make to music with our body.

- Amodal, affective or emotive gestures, including all the movements and/or mental images of movements associated with more global sensations of the music.

Our interest is on performance control gestures, that can be considered as a subcategory of “sound producing gestures”.

We consider a gesture, as a trajectory or succession of actions in the control space, performed by the musician. Not all the possible action trajectories, are of interest, so an identification of the musically relevant ones is necessary.

1.2.2 Performance Loop

During a performance, a small amount of symbolic information in the form of score or in the form of musical intention (when improvising), is transformed into a much larger amount of information in the form of sound. This process is carried out by several actors and stages, as showed in fig. 1.1.

Figure 1.1: Performance Loop

Synthesis techniques can be roughly divided into physical models that are centered on the production of the sound, and spectral models that are centered in sound perception. As is showed in figure 1.1, physical models are linked to the instrument, and spectral models to the listener.

But there is a third actor left: the Performer that generates actions. In synthesis of musical instrument performances, the most important part is, in fact, the succession of actions by the performer (that is, he gestures), that will shape the resulting sound. There is, therefore, a gap in existing models that is linked with the Performer: Gesture based models.

1.2.3 Degrees of control, degrees of autonomy

An interactive system such as an instrument, can have different degrees of control. In the case of the computer as instrument, we can provide it with different control interfaces with a degree of control that can go from a very

low degree, for example, a simple score consisting on a sequence of note pitch and note duration, where only those two parameters are controllable, to a highly controllable and intimate interface, like an electronic counterpart of an acoustic violin, where the same set of controls as in the acoustic version is available to the performer. In general, the selection of the degree of control is of crucial importance in order to define the system and it will depend on the requirements of the user and the application. A professional violinist would prefer to have the same interface as in an acoustic violin, but an amateur player would like to have an easier version of the interface, that not only is fed with a smaller subset of the controls, but that also prevents the musician from playing incorrectly, and a non musician would like to control very few of them.

Except for the first case, the system should provide the part of the sound that is not controlled. That is what in [10] is referred to “degrees of expressive autonomy”, applied to multimodal interactive systems, and is defined as “the amount of degrees of freedom that a director, a choreographer, a composer (or in general the designer of an application involving communication of expressive content) leaves to the system in order to make decisions about the most suitable expressive content to convey in a given moment and about the way to convey it (i.e., which expressive gestures have to be generated to convey it)”.

To which extent should we give the system expressive autonomy? In the case of synthesis of instrument performances the degree of autonomy has to provide the expressive content that is not provided by the control interface.

In this report we will focus on synthesis of violin from score, that is, from an interface with very low degree of control, so we will have to provide all the expressive content necessary for a natural synthesis. Nevertheless, we leave open the control interface, that could be an electronic violin, that is, an interface with a very high control degree.

1.2.4 Naturalness and Expressivity

Terms like sound quality, naturalness and expressivity will be referred to throughout this document. They can be considered as a whole, rather than single independent entities, but there are some differences that we will try to introduce.

A performance could be non-expressive but could sound natural. Naturalness is an intrinsic characteristic of the sound of the instrument. It is like a fingerprint of it, a common denominator to all sounds produced by the instrument, that makes it immediately recognizable by a listener. And it is not only a characteristic of the sound, but of the performance. The physical configuration of the instrument and of the performer, the way of playing, etc. are the constraints that give that specific identity to the sound of a performance with that instrument. And expressivity is more related with

the intentionality of the performer.

The boundaries between naturalness and expressivity become fuzzy in a performance. For instance, vibrato could be considered as a naturalness feature in a traditional performance because all the violinists use automatically vibrato, but it could be also considered as an intentional expressive resource.

In previous works naturalness has not received as much attention as expressivity. We should provide the synthesizer with expressive capabilities just like a performer has, but also and more important with a natural sound.

1.3 Motivation

The goal of this work is to improve the existing synthesis techniques of musical instrument performances, specifically for the violin family. A better understanding of the sound produced by a violin during a performance and the challenge of modeling such a complex system, conforms the main motivations.

The facts that the application of this research and the translation to a production stage is direct, are also very encouraging.

The main application would be a synthesis-from-score system, that could be used in different scenarios such as composition or media production for low cost arrangements. Many other less direct applications are possible, including an easier interface for sound generation than the traditional instrument and a performance codification protocol for transmission and storage.

It is also very interesting the idea of instrument extension, where both instrument and performance model could be extended. However, we believe it is very important to understand the internals of the traditional instrument, prior to its extension.

1.4 Outline

The remaining part of this document consists of three more chapters followed by the conclusion.

In the second chapter (*literature review*), we make a review of previous work in the main related areas to this research, focusing on sound synthesis techniques, violin acoustics, and musical gestures.

In the third chapter (*first contributions*), we present the first experiments covering the most important ideas of the work and their results, including measurement of performance actions, spectral sound transformations, source-radiator separation of the violin, and description of performance data in score, sound, and physical domains.

In the fourth chapter (*proposed approach*) we propose the architecture for a new synthesis approach, and we give the guidelines for future work.

Chapter 2

Review of Former Work

In this chapter, we present a review of the related disciplines to this research. The main concepts and ideas will be introduced together with their strengths and weaknesses.

2.1 Sound synthesis techniques

In this section we will briefly present the state of the art in sound synthesis, analyzing the advantages and disadvantages of each of the approaches.

It is not of our interest to give a thorough description of sound synthesis, as there are specific reports about the subject ([62], [60]), but we provide an overview to the topic in order to put our proposal in context.

2.1.1 Taxonomies

It is difficult to define a clear taxonomy to classify the synthesis techniques, because they depend on many characteristics that are not completely orthogonal.

One of the most used taxonomies is the classification into four categories suggested in [60](table 2.1): abstract algorithms, processing of recorded samples, spectral models, and physical models.

Abstract algorithms category is not of interest to synthesize an existing instrument or sound, and it is difficult to produce musically pleasing sounds by exploring the parameters of a mathematical expression.

Spectral modeling category can be seen as an evolution of processing recorded samples category, because the best way to improve transformations of recordings, is to understand their effect on hearing, and the closest representation of the sound to hearing is the spectrum. Sampling synthesis transforms samples in time domain and spectral synthesis processes samples in time and frequency domains.

Table 2.1: Digital Synthesis Techniques Taxonomy from [60]

Processed Recording	Spectral Model	Physical Model	Abstract Algorithm
Concrete	Aditive	Ruiz Strings	VCO, VCA, VCF
Wavetable Time	Wavetable Frequ.	Karlsplus-Strong Ext.	Some Music V
Sampling	Phase vocoder	Waveguide	Original FM
Vector	PARSHL	Modal	Feedback FM
Granular	Sines+Noise(Serra)	Cordis-Anima	Waveshaping
Princ. Comp. Time	Princ. Comp. Freq.	Mosaic	Phase Distortion
Wavelet	Chant		Karlsplus Strong
	VOSIM		
	Risset FM Brass		
	Chowning FM Voice		
	Subtractive		
	LPC		
	Inverse FFT		
	Xenakis Line Cluster		

If abstract methods are not considered and spectral modeling wraps sampling, this leaves only two main categories: physical-modeling and spectral-modeling. We will consider nevertheless sampling synthesis and spectral synthesis two different categories to better clarify our purpose. We propose a classification with three main categories (sampled based, spectral models and physical models) and a fourth one for mixed or hybrid models. These are models that share characteristics with the other categories and our model will belong to it.

Another example of taxonomy found in [52] differentiates the techniques in those that are based in concatenated samples and those that are parametric. Both physical and spectral models appear in the same subtree, “Parametric Synthesis” and spectral models are called “Signal Models” (fig. 2.1). This idea of parametrization against concatenation will appear in a latter discussion in section 2.1.3, as a parameter to subclassify spectral models.

Following we introduce the main synthesis techniques classified according to the proposed taxonomy: Sampling, Spectral, Physical and Hybrid models.

2.1.2 Sampled based synthesis

This techniques are based on playback of recorded samples, and transformations in time domain. The main techniques belonging to this group are cited next:

- Sampling synthesis, can be considered as an evolution of tape-based “musique concrète”. These techniques play a sequence of recorded sounds called samples. The level of realism and sound quality in individual samples is the highest possible, because there is no synthetic sound produced but recordings. But the problems come arise when

Figure 2.1: Digital Synthesis Techniques Taxonomy from [52]

the samples are played in sequence and when trying to slightly modify a sound: all the transitions and nuances so important in musical phrasing and expression that are not stored in the database, can not be synthesized. To make more flexible and controllable these techniques, some transformations are required. Theoretically, a sound can be transformed into another one by linear transformations, but this techniques work in time domain, so transformations and concatenations are not musically satisfactory, at least to date. One example of this type of synthesis is the “Vienna sound library” [2]. The quality is very high inside the same recording, but sometimes the concatenation of recordings is noticeable. The expressive control is very basic, restricted to the existing recordings. We will adopt from this group the advantages of having recorded samples.

- Wavetable in time domain, is based on the periodic repetition of stored waveshapes, in order to approximate the output sound to that of an instrument tone. Of course the result of the synthesis using only periodic sounds is not of interest when trying to imitate a traditional instrument, where a big component of the sound is non-periodic.
- Vector synthesis is essentially a multiple-wavetable synthesis method with interpolation.
- Principal-components synthesis. This method is based on the statistical Principal Component Analysis. Sounds are characterized by eigenvectors representing the “principal component waveshapes”, which can be mixed to provide an approximation to a sound.

2.1.3 Spectral models

We will consider spectral models those that rely on the spectral properties of the sound, that is, on the perceptual side of the sound and not on the production of the sound.

This definition covers a wide range of possible models. Following we cite the most relevant ones:

- Linear Predictive Coding. More than a synthesis technique it is an estimator for the coefficients of a all-pole filter, but it has been used successfully for speech and music synthesis. LPC can be viewed as one of many possible nonlinear smoothings of the short-time power spectrum, with good audio properties.
- Subtractive Synthesis, refers to linear filtering of an input signal so that some frequency components are attenuated (subtracted) and some emphasized. A better term is source-filter model since the basic idea of subtractive synthesis is that sound production is divided into two parts: an excitation signal (source) and a resonator (filter). The excitation is typically a spectrally rich waveform, such as noise or some periodic pulse-form whose spectrum has energy at several frequencies. The filter not only attenuates some of the frequency components of the input but also boost some of them. This can be used to imitate formants which are resonances that characterize the timbre of an instrument. In analog synthesizers this principle was very popular.
- Additive synthesis, covers a type of analysis-driven techniques that basically add a number of sine waves to construct a desired spectrum. One of the advantages of additive synthesis is the availability of a corresponding analysis technique, the Fourier Transform, which takes as input a signal waveform and generates the frequency, amplitude and phase of each sinusoidal that contributes to the input signal. Furthermore, it exists a very efficient way to compute the Fourier Transform, the FFT, making the analysis stage much faster. These data can be used as parameters that can be controlled, modified and finally resynthesized. For the synthesis we can use the inverse of the FFT, obtaining a waveform from the analysis parameters. The result of the analysis is a model that consists on a set of discrete “lines” corresponding to the evolution in time of sinusoids, each sinusoid corresponding with the harmonics of the sound.

The first examples of analysis-synthesis of music based on additive parameters are from [44]. The most general representation of spectral models is the STFT (Short Time Fourier Transform, [3]) applies FFT to overlapping windows of the signal. Sinusoidal: The next level of abstraction is the sinusoidal model [33], that represents time-varying

spectra as sums of time-varying sinusoids. Both harmonic and inharmonic sounds can be parameterized in this way but the analysis is particularly efficient with harmonic sounds that have clear and stable harmonics. Musical sounds are not totally harmonic, they also contain noise, as bow noise in bowed instruments, breath noise, in wind instruments, etc. Several techniques have approached the separation and resynthesis of noise elements, for speech ([27]) or music applications as in Sinusoidal plus Residual([56]). In this approach the sinusoids only model the stable partials of a sound and the residual, or its approximation, models what is left, ideally an stochastic component. It is less general than either the STFT or the Sinusoidal representations but it results in an enormous gain in flexibility when controlling and making transformations. SMS (Spectral modeling synthesis) is a framework for analysis, transformation and resynthesis based on the Sinusoidal plus Residual model.

Higher level spectral representation based is achieved by extracting high level information such as pitch, spectral shape, vibrato, or attack characteristics.

An extension to sines+noise models is reported in [65], where the signal is represented as sines, transients and noise.

The latter technique, additive synthesis, is the most interesting for our purpose and from now on, references to spectral modeling will refer to it, and specifically to SMS.

As showed in 2.1, another synthesis taxonomy [52] is presented, that divides the techniques into concatenative and parametrical. We will use this parameter to distinguish among different spectral models.

As we can see in fig 2.2, there is a range of possible techniques that goes from quasi sample based techniques (i.e: concatenative spectral models), to fully parametrical models that do not use samples at all, but a model of the sound of the instrument (i.e: parametrical spectral models). Concatenative synthesis refer to techniques that use recorded samples and concatenate them to form complete phrases, trying to capture the articulation of musical sounds. See [53] for a summary of these techniques.

Methods at the beginning of the range (fig. 2.2), try to synthesize sounds from the spectral analysis of recordings. The analysis gives a set of perceptual parameters of the sound that can be modified and re-synthesized again. These parameters can be modified through transformations and the resulting sound will be similar to the original but with the modifications applied. High quality transformations are possible, at different levels, from frame-level to semantic transformations. Time, pitch, rhythm, genre, tonality, are examples of characteristics that can be transformed. Provided with high quality spectral transformations we can cover a wider sound space than the

Figure 2.2: Quality vs Parametrization

one of the recordings, and build high quality synthesizers. In fact, the best existing ones are based on this methodology. Examples are Vocaloid [7] a voice synthesizer and Synful[30] a general instrument synthesizer.

Other methods go further towards parametrization (fig. 2.2). This has a lot of advantages, such as higher degree of control, and smaller database of recordings. Higher degree of control allows to improve expressivity and thus, sound quality in a performance. The problem is that to build a model that avoids using recordings is a very difficult task and a lot of research has to be done. To date, existing synthesizers that go towards modelization loose the quality of the recordings. An example is, Salto [19], a saxophone synthesizer has high degree of control, but low sound quality. It seems that there is a tradeoff between parametrization and sound quality.

The perfect model would be a fully parametrical one, with the sound quality of a recording. Our model will try to follow this principle. Starting at a point using a small set of transformations that can modify the samples without compromising the quality, we will go towards more parametrization as far as the sound quality is almost comparable with the recordings as showed in fig. 2.2.

In figure 2.2 we can see a representation of the spectral model space and an approximate location of existing synthesizers and models, as well as our proposal.

There exist other methods such as data-driven synthesis([52], [24], [48]), concatenative synthesis ([52]), that lie also in the group of spectral modeling.

Spectral representations and transformations

SMS. SMS is a set of techniques and software implementations for the analysis, transformation and synthesis of musical sounds based on [56]. The aim of SMS is to get general and musically meaningful sound representa-

tions based on analysis, from which musical parameters might be manipulated while maintaining high quality sound. These techniques can be used for synthesis, processing and coding applications, while some of the intermediate results might also be applied to other music related problems, such as sound source separation, musical acoustics, music perception, or performance analysis. In [4] an implementation of SMS in Matlab is described, with transformations such as filtering, pitch transposition, time stretch, vibrato and tremolo, spectral shape shift, gender change, harmonizer, hoariness and morphing.

Pitch shift/timestretch. Pitch Shifting is a way to change the pitch of a signal without changing its length while preserving its harmonic relationship and timbre. Time Compression/Expansion, also known as “Time Stretching” is the reciprocal process to Pitch Shifting. It leaves the pitch of the signal intact while changing its speed (tempo).

There are several fairly good methods to do time compression/expansion and pitch shifting but most of them will not perform well on all different kinds of signals and for any desired amount of shift/stretch ratio. Typically, good algorithms allow pitch shifting up to 5 semitones on average and stretching the length by 130%. When time stretching and pitch shifting single instrument recordings we might even be able to achieve a 200% time stretch, or a one-octave pitch shift with no audible loss in quality.

The main techniques for Time Compression/Expansion and Pitch Shifting, are the following:

- Phase Vocoder and extensions. The phase vocoder (name derived from voice encoder) is firstly introduced by Flanagan and Golgen in 1966 ([16]). It is based on the STFT that returns the frequency domain representation of the signal at a fixed frequency grid. The time scale of the signal is changed in frequency domain, and then an iSTFT is done to regain the time domain representation of the signal, allowing for high-quality time-scale modification of the original sound. The basic phase vocoder suffers from a severe drawback because it introduces a considerable amount of audible artifacts as “smearing” and “reverberation”. Extensions to the basic phase vocoder are reported in [40] and [28] with the denomination of Phase-Lock vocoder, or Spectral Peak Scaling in [8].
- Time Domain Harmonic Scaling (TDHS), are techniques on time domain, based on the work by Rabiner and Schafer in 1978 ([41]). It is based on a correct estimate of the fundamental frequency of the sound processed. The time scale is changed by copying the input to the output in an overlap-and-add manner (therefore it’s also sometimes referred to as ‘(P)SOLA’ - (pitch) synchronized overlap-add method).

RPLHN RPLHN stands for “Residual pitch, loudness, and harmonics + noise”. It is a spectral representation of sound used in the Synful synthesizer ([30]). It consists on storing only the rapid fluctuations of pitch and loudness of each of the harmonics of the harmonic part of the sound, together with the residual. This synthesizer is fed with a MIDI stream consisting on basically note-on, note-off, and velocity messages. This is what they call slowly-varying frequencies and amplitudes. To generate rapid fluctuations of parameters typical in a musical performance, they use recordings of musical phrases, represented in RPLHN format, allowing the synthesis of complete idiomatic musical phrases independent of pitch and amplitude.

2.1.4 Physically based synthesis

Physically based synthesis methods are methods that focus on the production of the sound instead of the perception of it. They are mathematical models that describe the physical acoustics of instrumental sound production. They are used both to simulate the sound-producing mechanisms of existing instruments and to create sounds of fanciful instruments that would otherwise be impossible to build. A review paper about physical modeling techniques is found in [67].

A fundamental principle of physical modeling synthesis is the interaction between an exciter and a resonator. An excitation is an action that causes vibration, such as the stroke of a bow, the hit of a stick, or a blow air. A resonance is the response of the body of an instrument to the excitation signal. In general, the exciter has a nonlinear behavior, and the resonator has a linear behavior.

They are theoretically the most powerful methods, in the sense that if we could know the exact physic-acoustic behavior of an instrument we could synthesize its sound production. But it would be computationally expensive and even if we could find a trustworthy model computationally cheap, we would need to control each of the parameters. And to get a realistic and expressive sound is quite difficult, sometimes requiring the same interface to control it as for the acoustic instrument counterpart, that is, the instrument itself. One of the main problems in physical modeling is how to extract and control expressive performance parameters. See [14], [29] for more about it.

These techniques work in temporal and space domains. Depending on the object modeled, the spatial dimension can be 1-D for strings, 2-D for membranes and plates, and 3-D for room acoustics.

Models are always just an approximation of real physical phenomena. Therefore, they reduce the complexity of the target system. This may be desired for a number of reasons, such as keeping the computational cost manageable. These constraints are particularly important in real-time sound synthesis and simulation. Complexity can be reduced taking into account

perceptual characteristics of the sound. For example, phenomena that are physically relevant but does not have an audible effect can be excluded.

In the following, we will briefly introduce the main techniques belonging to this category. A more detailed description of physical models can be found at [57].

- Difference equations are usually used when describing how a signal changes over time. In modeling a phenomenon this way, the first step is to find the smallest number of variables that can accurately describe the state of the modeled phenomenon. The next step sets up the simplest difference equations that are precise descriptions of the laws governing the changes in these variables.
- Vibrating Mass-spring networks. This group of techniques (also referred to as mass-interaction, cellular or particle systems) decompose the original physical system in its structural atoms (masses and springs). Vibrating media are modeled by a net of interconnected masses that interact among them (action-reaction). Vibrating media are also elastic: if any part of the medium is displaced from its position of equilibrium, a restoring force immediately appears and tries to push it back. This in turn causes the neighboring positions to move, and so on, causing a process called wave propagation.
- Modal Synthesis is an alternative to the mass-spring paradigm. It starts from the premise that a sound-producing object can be represented as a collection of vibrating substructures. The number of substructures is usually very small in comparison with those in the mass-spring approach. The substructures can be excited in different mode of vibration. A mode in an object corresponds to the sound it produces when it is excited in a particular point. A modal vibration description of an object is the set of N nodes corresponding to N coordinates over the geometry of the object. The mode data can be obtained through the spectral analysis exciting the object in the desired points. This is very interesting because mixes Physical models with Spectral models.
- Waveguide Synthesis [59]. The aim in digital waveguide modeling is to design computationally efficient models that behave like physical systems. A particularly nice feature of the digital waveguide approach is that it simulates physical phenomena directly in a building-blocks way. The basics of this Method is a simple algorithm for the synthesis of plucked string sounds, the Karplus-Strong algorithm [25]. It is based on the idea that a wavetable, i.e. a table containing a sampled waveform of an audio signal, is modified while it is read. This technique is especially well suited to the simulation of 1D resonators, such as a

vibrating string, a narrow acoustic tube, or a thin bar, but there is extension to it called waveguide-meshes, that are used to model 2-D and 3-D objects.

Physical models are widely used to model instruments such as guitar([29]), clavichord([66]) and there exist also models for the violin or parts of it (strings, bridge, bow-string interaction): [58], [21] and [55]. Other attempts try to model the body of instruments using multidimensional waveguide-meshes in ([38], [22] and [17]).

There are also other techniques that do not rely so much on physics or acoustics, but that are somehow “inspired” on the physical properties of the instrument [49]. Our approach will be partly inside this “physically inspired” category.

Our model is basically a spectral model, but some ideas such as source-radiator separation, physical actions as controls, and some analysis of the acoustics of the violin will be incorporated to improve the model.

2.1.5 Hybrid models

There are also some attempts to synthesize instrument sounds that do not fit into the categories above, because they combine features of the main categories, that is, physical and spectral models. In [49], physical controls from a violin bow, are matched to parameters of a spectral model. In [72] and [71] a hybrid model of a flute is presented using a combination of a physical model simulating the resonator and a signal model simulating the source of the instrument sound. Commuted digital waveguides ([59]) is an extension to the physical technique “Digital Waveguides”, that uses sound samples of the excitation of the instrument as input to the model, so it can be somehow considered a hybrid approach.

Our model will belong to this category, since it will share features from both spectral and physical models.

2.2 Violin acoustics

In this section we give an overview of the acoustics of the violin. Physical models are models that simulate the behavior of the acoustics of the instruments. Although our approach is not purely physical, it will take into account some of its characteristics. An exhaustive description of violin physics can be found in [13].

2.2.1 Main parts of the violin

A musical instrument can be seen as the association of an exciter and a vibrating body. In the case of the violin, the exciter is the bow and the vibrating body is composed by:

- The string, that is a highly resonant structure and works as a vibrator but does not produce sound.
- The sounding structure (body and air cavity), that is a broadly resonant structure, that acts as a sound radiator.

Vibrating bodies are mostly linear, passive(dissipate energy), and harmonically resonating structures. The excitation in the violin is essentially non-linear, sustained and drives expressivity. Exciter and vibrating body interact in a very complex way.

In fig. 2.3 we can see a diagram of the main physical blocks during a violin performance. There are two loops, the main loop, begins with the musician bowing, then the bow excites the string, the string excites the body, the body radiates the sound into the room, where the sound arrives as feedback again to the musician. The internal loop represents the interaction between the strings and the bow.

Figure 2.3: Two-loop Diagram of the Violin

The internal loop represents the dynamic part of the sound system. A model of this interaction is the objective of the synthesis. This idea inspired the separation of the synthesis in two parts, as discussed in section 2.2.5:

- the sound source, corresponding to the inner loop, that is, the interaction string-bow. It is the dynamic part, the part that drives the expressivity.
- the sound radiator, corresponding to the body of the violin. It can be considered static. It gives the color to the timbre.

The separation in these two blocks, means having a spectral model of the source, and a model of the radiator. This approach has a lot of advantages such as not depending on sound recordings for the spectral analysis, transformations with higher quality, and the possibility to extend the model playing with parameters of the radiator.

2.2.2 String vibrations

Transverse motion

From the three types of vibration that occur in a string (transversal, longitudinal and rotational) the most relevant one is the transversal one.

A string can be represented as an unidimensional element along the x axe, hold with a longitudinal Tension T , and mass density ϵ . Be $\eta(x, t)$ the transversal position of point x in time t , the wave equation is the following:

$$c^2 \frac{d^2 \eta}{dx^2} = \frac{d^2 \eta}{t^2} \quad (2.1)$$

where celerity: $c = \sqrt{\frac{T}{\epsilon}}$

Digital waveguides [57] are efficient computational models for physical media through which acoustic waves propagate. They carry the traveling wave equation into the “digital domain”, by sampling $\eta(x, t)$ in a point xi at intervals of P seconds, corresponding to a sampling rate $fs = 1/P$. That is, a digital waveguide is a delay line, with sampled values of the displacement of the string. Other variables than displacement (velocity, acceleration, slope) are possible.

For finite string with fixed ends, a string has harmonically related eigenfrequencies:

$$f_n = n \frac{c}{2L} = n f_0 \quad (2.2)$$

where L is string length and f_0 fundamental frequency.

For a more realistic model we should take into account thickness, stiffness and moving ends of the string. This effects, induce an increase in the inharmonicity and dispersion. Harmonic relation for a stiff string model is as follows:

$$f_n = n f_0 \sqrt{1 + B n^2}, B = \frac{\pi^3 E d^4}{64 L^2 T} \quad (2.3)$$

B is the inharmonicity coefficient, and depends to a large extent on the diameter (d) of the string. When the string is vibrating, there is a curvature, and if the string has a thickness of radio r , the longitude of the string increases along the curvature.

2.2.3 Bowed string motion and friction

The motion of the bowed string and the interaction between both is a very complex system. To simplify it, we will initially consider only transverse waves, the string has fixed ends, and no thickness (is perfectly flexible). The bow is rigid, and the contact string-bow will be considered as a single point. This is of course a very simple model, but some features could be of help in analyzing and synthesizing violin sounds. In fig. 2.4 we can see a schema of this simplified model with the main parameters that control the vibration of the string: bow pressure (F_p), bow-bridge distance (βL) and bow velocity (v_b).

Figure 2.4: Bowed String Model

Regimes of motion

There are two main types of interaction between string and bow: sticking and slipping, and its configuration in time will define the regime of motion of the string:

- Stick: The bow is pressed against the string and pulled across it. Due to the friction of the rosin with the string, it sticks with the bow. The bow carries the string (the move with the same velocity), until the tension of the string is bigger than the friction.
- Slip: The friction breaks, letting the string slip under the bow. When the string is close to the position of equilibrium, it sticks again to the bow.

Depending on the actions of the performer, the temporal succession and duration of these interactions will vary and we can obtain several different regimes of motion.

Figure 2.5: Helmholtz motion: position, velocity, and force spectrum

In 1973, J.C Schelleng [46] established a diagram (fig. 2.6) identifying the main regimes of motion. Among them, he identified the Helmholtz motion regime. Helmholtz motion is the most accepted model for bowed strings, and represents the regular motion in a classical performance. Out of this region, the sound is traditionally not considered musically acceptable. It models the bowed string as two straight lines connected by an angle that propagates, from one side to the other, following a parabolic trajectory (fig. 2.5). It is a periodic motion with period $T = 2L/c$, where the bow slips and sticks repeatedly. The sticking phase corresponds to the interval in which the angle moves between the bow and the nut and during which the string sticks to the bow hair and therefore takes the speed of the bow. The slipping phase corresponds to the interval in which the angle moves between the bow and the bridge and during which the string moves in opposite direction to that of the bow.

Schelleng's diagram shows how the Helmholtz motion can be maintained in function of the bow-bridge distance and bow force on the string, for a constant velocity: The closer to the bridge, the more difficult to maintain it. The maximum force is limited by the flattening effect and amount of noise. Minimum force is limited by the amount of noise and bridge mobility. In the following equation we can see the maximum and minimum force according to Schelleng. Z is characteristic impedance of the string:

$$F_{max} = Z \frac{v_b}{\beta}, F_{min} = Z^2 \frac{v_b^2}{\beta} \quad (2.4)$$

In addition to Helmholtz regime, Shellen's diagram identifies other regions called "raucous" or "higher modes" (fig. 2.6).

Extensions of Schellen's Diagram have been reported in [54], and other regimes are identified(fig. 2.7):

- Multiple slips. The bow force is not high enough to allow the bow to stick throughout the nominal sticking period of the Helmholtz motion.
- Anomalous low frequency. A periodic note with a lower pitch can be produced with a control of the bow force that makes the transversal waves to miss a slip opportunity few times in the stick-slip motion.
- Non-periodic motions: Irregular motion obtained when the bow force is too high.

Of all the possible regimes of motion, we are only interested in synthesizing the one traditionally considered as musically acceptable, the so called Helmholtz motion.

In this regime the spectrum of the force acting on the bridge is fixed. The frequency of the motion is that of the string. It does not depend on the bowing parameters. The amplitude of the motion (and thus, of the sound level) depends mainly on the bow velocity.

Until the stable Helmholtz motion is reached, there is a region called pre-Helmholtz transient. Studies and simulations about the obtention and duration of the transient have been reported by Woodhouse, Schumacher and Guettler. This transient is translated into the sound domain as note attack and intra-note transition.

Figure 2.6: Schelleng's Diagram

Figure 2.7: Extended Schelleng's Diagram from [54]. x axis=bow position, y-axis=bow force

2.2.4 Sound projection

Sound is radiated from the violin in all directions. Sound radiation is a very complex phenomena that depends on the properties of the sound source, mainly its size and frequency. The relation size/frequency determines largely the properties of the radiation. For a diameter(meters) of the sound source, smaller than $100(Hz * m) / frequency(Hz)$ (DG measure, as defined in [64]), the sound is radiated with equal strength in all directions, and for a longer diameter the radiation becomes more directed and complex. At low frequencies, the sound remains around the object, and little is projected, and at higher frequencies most of the sound is radiated.

The violin radiates in all directions for low frequencies, but for high frequencies the radiation is more directional and different for each frequency. This can be easily seen in the spectra of sounds recorded in different directions and positions. See fig. 2.8

Figure 2.8: Main radiation directions for the violin (after Meyer)[64]

Sound projection models are used in different applications. In [12], a database of directional impulse responses is collected for several instruments, to build directional radiation models for physical models, and to add more realistic body resonances to electronic stringed instruments for real-time performance. An application of this directional models is BoSSA (Bowed-Sensor-Speaker-Array) [63] a bow controlled instrument with directional sound projection.

2.2.5 Source-Radiator Separation

Assuming that the body of a violin behaves as a linear mechanic-acoustic system, transforming input forces applied by the strings on the bridge into acoustic pressure waves irradiated through the air, we can consider the violin composed by two parts: sound source and sound radiator (section 2.2.1) and model separately each of them. This can be of great help in order to simplify problems with sound radiation and signal transformation as we will see later.

The body acts as a filter that transforms the source signal. The obtained sound is the convolution of source signal and body filter response. The separation of them can be achieved by different techniques. We can measure one of them, and extract the other one by signal deconvolution, or measure both. Measurement of the violin body, can be done by measuring its impulse response, and measurement of the sound source, can be done by measuring the force exerted by the strings on the bridge.

Separation of violin signal into source and radiator, appears in the literature in different contexts. In [15] they make a subjective comparison of the quality of violins, by extracting the source signal from a recording, and convolving this signal with the impulse response of different violins. In [18] they try to find correlates between violin acoustics and sound perception, in order to improve the quality in violin making.

Modeling the body

Considering that the violin body behaves as a linear system, we can model it as a filter with a specific impulse response in time domain or frequency response in frequency domain. The frequency response of a system such as a violin is found by exciting it with a known signal and measuring the resulting vibration or sound pressure level. Several types of excitation signals may be used as long as the excitation signal contains enough power at all frequencies that are of interest. Mechanical transducers placed on the violin will change the frequency response of the measurement. While the software may correct for the influence of the transducer(s) in many cases, it is still preferred to use transducer(s) of low weight or no-contact sensors.

Excitation. How is it excited? The main methods for exciting the violin (table 2.2) as summarized in [34] are described in the following :

- bowing. This is the normal way to excite the violin. The frequency response could be determined recording a chromatic scale. But it is difficult to play all the notes with equal force, velocity, bow position, etc, and the response will only contain the partials of the played tones. This could be compensated by paying a glissando at constant velocity. This could be achieved by a bowing machine, but not by a musician, that can not control all the bowing parameters to be constant.

- finger tapping, traditionally used, is easier to control and generates a short pulse excitation with sufficient power on the desired frequency range, similar to a Delta function.
- hammer in a pendulum. with this method the reproducibility is excellent: the hammer hits always with same force, position and direction.
- Impulse hammer, is the professional tool. Wide range of power frequency
- Loudspeaker. It can also be used to excite the violin but it is not suitable for sound pressure measurements since the loudspeaker also radiates directly to the microphone.

Excitation signal	Repeatability	Price	Frequency range
Played glissando	Fair	Zero	>196 Hz
Finger tapping	Good	Zero	200 - 3000 Hz
Impulse Hammer	Very good	High	20 - 20000 Hz

Table 2.2: Excitation signals. From [34]

Where is it excited? Which resonances are excited and how much they are excited depend on where the excitation is exerted. The excitation source should be done as close as possible to where the strings are fastened to the bridge, the same place as the player does when bowing.

Response of the excitation: Measurement. By exciting the body of the violin, we put it into vibration that produces sound pressure. We can either measure vibration or sound pressure. Vibration can be measured as displacement, velocity or acceleration. By integration/differentiation we can go from one magnitude to the other. Usually displacement transducers are less immune to noise in high frequencies, because the spectrum decays 40 dB per decade compared to acceleration. Transducers can be attached to the body, and thus, modifying its response, or as in the case of optical transducers, they have no contact at all, providing better measurements.

Several solutions to measure the body response are reported: In [12] they record directional impulse responses of instruments using a rack of microphones positioned around the instrument. In [6] they use an accelerometer that gets the vibration at a point of the body structure. This method is not of our interest, because the measure is only in one point and the accelerometer is in contact with the body, and thus, it changes the vibration modes. In [18] they use a laser to measure mobility of the body in one point.

Violin body resonances. The response of the violin is characterized by its resonances or modes, and can be visualized as peaks in the spectrum.

The way of identifying the modes of the violin described in [64], has become a standard in the field. They classify the modes as follows:

- A modes, caused by the motion of enclosed air. When the body is vibrating, the volume of the body is changing and thus, air is pressed out and sucked into. The A0 resonance corresponds with the resonant frequency of the whole volume resonator.
- B modes, are motion modes of the back plate.
- T modes, are due to motion primarily of the top plate.
- C modes, refer to bending and flexing modes of the “corpus” or body.
- N mode, is the resonance of the neck.

The most important of all of them are represented as peaks in the spectrum as: A0 resonance around 270Hz, P1 between 400 and 500 Hz, P2 between 500 and 600 Hz and the BH (Bridge hill) a smoothed hill (not a peak) between 2 and 3kHz (fig. 2.9 from [18]).

Figure 2.9: Main resonances of the violin

Representation of the body. Several techniques are possible to parameterize the model of the body:

- Sampled Impulse Response of the body or frequency response: The direct way to do it. Recordings of the body after being excited by an impulse, that is, the impulse response of the body.

- Linear time-invariant Filter Approximation: Several techniques are known in order to approximate the impulse response of a resonant body with a filter [58]. Some of them will be tested.
- Modal analysis/synthesis is basically a collection of parallel high-resonance bandpass filters, excited by an input impulse. Each filter has three parameters: frequency, resonance (decay time), and output level. It is especially good for simulating struck sounds, like rods, bars, and plates, and objects with low number of modes. As the violin has a very high number of modes (specially in the high frequencies), this method could allow to approximate the low frequency modes in the violin.

Modeling the source signal

The source signal can be either extracted by deconvolving the body impulse response from the whole signal as in [15], or by directly measuring it as in [58] and [18] where they measure the force exerted by the strings on the bridge using small force transducers placed between the bridge and the strings (see fig.2.10).

Figure 2.10: Measuring the source signal. Figure from [18]

Deconvolution is the inverse function of convolution. Be $s(t)$ the source signal, $h(t)$ the filter representing the impulse response of the body, and $v(t)$ the sound of the violin, $s(t) \oplus h(t) = v(t)$, or in frequency domain $S(f) * H(f) = V(f)$

If we know $h(t)$ and $v(t)$, we can extract $s(t)$ as follows: $s(t) = v(t) \oplus h(t)^{-1}$

So the problem reduces to find the inverse filter of the violin body. But not all filters are invertible. In the case of the violin body, it has mixed phase

impulse response, so it is not directly invertible, and we need an approximation. In [35] a solution to invert filters with mixed phase is proposed.

2.3 Performance actions and gestures

2.3.1 Musical gesture

Musical instruments are controlled by performers through physical actions. The quality of the performance depends to a larger extent on those actions performed by the player than on the instrument itself. It is therefore a crucial factor in order to improve existing synthesizers, the understanding of those available controls, and how are they used in order to get control of the sound.

We will consider a gesture, as a trajectory or succession of actions in the control space, performed by the musician.

2.3.2 Performer actions

Research carried out in acoustics show that the main control parameters of a violin are bow speed, distance between bow and bridge and bow force on the strings. These parameters are strongly correlated to sound characteristics. Therefore, we may expect that focusing on these parameters brings considerable information on the invariance and variability of bow strokes.

As found in the literature, and contrasted with the experience of violin players we can identify the main controls as follows (fig. 2.11):

- Right-hand controls: Normally the bow is controlled with the right-hand, and the main related controls are bow-bridge distance, bow transversal position, bow velocity, bow acceleration, bow pressure, bow hair width, bow tilt, rosin and string being played.
- Left-hand controls: Position of the finger on the string and Vibrato.

In the following, the main controls are introduced, and the main techniques to measure them are discussed.

2.3.3 Sensors

Several sensing channels have been exploited for capturing musical gesture. See [45] for an excellent summary of used sensors in existing musical interfaces:

- Capacitive sensing, a technique part of a broader one called “electric field sensing”, consist of an antenna connected to an “LC” tank oscillator, with frequency determined by the reactance of a network composed of an inductance (L) and capacitance (C). By moving an object into the vicinity of this sense antenna, the effective capacitance of the antenna increases, thus shifting the oscillation frequency ($w1$) of the LC tank (see fig.2.12). This technique is the basis of the Theremin

Figure 2.11: Main violin controls

and it is often used for measuring bow position, [36], [47], [69]. In these works, the bow is covered with a resistive material. Two electric signals are sent from each extremity of the bow at different frequencies and are gradually attenuated along the bow stick by the resistance. The positions are then computed according to the strength of the two signals.

- Ultrasonic sensors, are used to measure distance and motion
- Optical sensors, that range from simple light-emitting diode (LED), photodiode, photosensor arrays, and video cameras with complicated image processing.
- Radar and microwave motion sensors have also been occasionally used to measure musical performances.

2.3.4 Bow position and velocity

With bow position we mean the position of the bow when it is in contact with the string, measured in two dimensions: perpendicular to the string (from now on, bow position), and the distance from the bow to the bridge

Figure 2.12: LC oscillator

(or bow-bridge distance). As for the position we are also interested in its derivatives velocity and acceleration.

Both dimensions are generally measured the same way.

The main methods found in the literature are the following:

- Based on capacitive sensing technique, antennas are mounted on the bridge and track the position of the bow [36], [47], [69]
- String and Bow fed with current in the form of a Wheatstone bridge [5]. The bow has a thin resistance wire inserted among the wires which is divided in two parts by the string, each of those parts constituting one branch of a Wheatstone bridge. The same way, the string is divided in two parts by the wire, to constitute the other branch of the bridge. fig.2.13

Figure 2.13: Wheatstone Bridge to measure bow position by Askenfelt

- Accelerometers as in [43], see fig. 2.14
- Combination between accelerometers and video camera, as in [50].

Figure 2.14: Hyperbow from IRCAM

The first one seems to be more intrusive, the sound in the second one can not be used for synthesis purposes because of the wire in the bow making contact with the string. The most promising methodology seems to be with wireless accelerometers, but they only provide the transversal acceleration. The last one is an improvement of the third one with a complementary measurement in order to measure the position of the bow.

2.3.5 Bow force

. Bow force is meant to be the force exerted by the bow on the string, but due to the complexity of measuring it, alternative solutions that give an approximation to this parameter are found.

We find in the literature the following approaches:

- Force exerted by the violinist with the forefinger. This can be achieved by fixing a “Force Sensing Resistor” on the bow under the forefinger of the player. This approach is used in [47].
- Measuring the strain of the bow stick. In [70] they fix two strain gauges at the middle point of the bow, in two directions, to capture downward and lateral strain of the bow stick. See fig.2.16
- Measuring the strain of the bow hair. In [5] they use a pair of strain gauges at both ends of the bow hair, and compute the bow force using a wheatstone bridge as for computing the bow position.

Acoustical studies of the physical controls of the violinist and its effect on the sound produced, show that the most relevant parameters in sound production, are in fact, those described previously: bow position, bow-bridge distance and bow velocity. Other parameters such as string being played, and fingering can be extracted directly from the spectral analysis as in [26].

Figure 2.15: Capacitive sensing bow

Figure 2.16: Hyperbow at MIT [70]

Some parameters such as bow hair width in contact with the string, resin and bow tilt, are (if even) approximated.

2.3.6 Analysis of gestures

In the previous section we described the main controls that are available to the violinist. Those controls are never articulated isolated, but grouped in entities that we call performance gesture. We find in [6] and [5], an analysis of typical bow gestures, such as bow strokes (legato, détaché, staccato, saltato), dynamics gestures (crescendo, diminuendo) and others.

A description of some common bow strokes is showed in table 2.3. Basically there are three parameters to classify the bow strokes: degree of accentuation (from smooth to percussive), degree of legato (from legato to single note) and velocity or note duration.

Bow Stroke	Description
Legato	Smoothly connected notes, normally in the same bow
Portato	Short series of gently pulsed legato notes
Detaché	Each note in a separate stroke, with constant speed and smooth attack
Staccato	Shortened detaché with initial accent, the bow remaining on the string. Often used with slurs, as a series of short stopped notes played in the same bow.
Martelé	Almost percussive attack followed by quick release. The notes are separated, and bow remains on the string
Spiccato	Off-the-string, bouncing bow stroke, producing a crisp sound
Saltato	Bow bounces naturally off the string. Lighter, more rapid and less percussive than spiccato.
Tremolo	Very short rapid bow strokes, moving the bow back and forth for the duration of the note.

Table 2.3: Common bow strokes

2.3.7 Expressivity

When performing from a musical score, some variations from the score are introduced. Some of these variations form part of the expressive intentionality of the performer, while others are due to the experience, technique and skill of the player, or because of the physical constraints of the instrument and the player. See 1.2.4 for an explanation about differences between expressivity and what we called naturalness.

These deviations from the score are what we understand as expressivity and is the essence of the music itself. That is why we prefer the performance of a professional musician, rather than the performance of a student, or of a computer. Even in the case that the computer is able to simulate realistically the sound of the instrument, the performance can be considered as not musically valid.

The same way as we decided to synthesize whole gestures instead of concatenating single notes, can be extrapolated to a higher level to favour expressivity in a musical phrase against concatenation of gestures to form the same phrase. Although our approach is centered in capturing naturalness of gestures, a model of expressivity in a higher temporal level such as musical phrase is of great interest, in order to concatenate all the gestures in a musical interesting way.

The main contributions in musical expressivity are summarized next:

Human Expert rules

In [61] is proposed an expressivity model composed by performance rules that model different expressive features like phrasing, note grouping, rules that are proposed by “human experts”, and that are refined through process called “analysis by synthesis”, in which comparisons of real performances with the predicted by the set of rules are recursively made.

Automatic learning techniques

In this group we include performance models that apply techniques of Artificial Intelligence such as machine learning and data mining in order to gather performance rules. In [68] they apply these learning techniques to articulations and dynamics in musical performances. In [42] they use inductive machine learning to predict onsets, duration, and dynamics. Genetic algorithms are also used to model expressive time and dynamics deviations in [20]. In [9] they make use of artificial neural networks that try to imitate the expressive style of analyzed piano performers.

Other approaches

Other techniques propose an expressivity model which try to find a parallelism between the motion of the human body and musical expressivity. In [32] they propose a Case Base Reasoning approach to generate expressive musical performances.

Chapter 3

First Contributions

In this chapter we present the first experiments covering the most important ideas of the work and their results, including measurement of performance actions, spectral sound transformations, source-radiator separation of the violin, and description of performance data in score, sound, and physical domains.

3.1 Performance data description

As described in section 1.2.2, musical information is transformed during a performance from musical notation to physical actions and finally to sound.

As we saw in section 2.1.2, spectral models are based in spectral transformations of sound samples stored in a database. We like the idea of using recorded samples to take advantage of the inherent properties of the recordings, but we propose to store expressive musical phrases of a real performance instead of single notes or parts of notes. Furthermore, we propose to have a database of musical phrases stored in the three information domains, that is, score, physical actions and spectral descriptors.

A first corpus for the database is build as follows: The phrases consist of musical exercises including different note-articulation patterns, tempos and dynamics. Articulation patterns go from single stressed notes, to different types of transitions between two notes, going through different bow strokes in groups of notes. Note duration ranges from whole notes to semi-quaver notes. Short notes (quaver and semiquaver) are grouped in duplets, triplets and quadruplets. Long notes are played legato in two bows, legato in one bow, staccato, martelle, crescendo and decrescendo. Shorter notes are grouped with different combinations of legato, détaché, saltato, spiccato. Another exercise combines notes of different duration in the same articulation pattern. We try to cover the most used articulation patterns in a traditional performance (see table 2.3).

Recordings were made at 100bpm, the violin tuned to A4=440Hz, using

a microphone, a video camera and with the sensors as described in section 3.2.3

The description of each type of information is aimed to facilitate comparison and selection of the most similar gesture to the required from all the gestures stored in the database, as well as aimed to decide the necessary transformations to be applied to the selected gesture.

Notice that the representation of the data in three different domains allows to go from one to another. It would be possible to go from score to sound, as we do in this work, as well as from sound to score, that is, for transcription. If the inputs to the synthesizer are physical actions and the output is sound, we could have a synthesizer controlled via a traditional instrument with sensors.

3.1.1 Score description

The score is described hierarchically in phrases that contain gestures which contain other gestures or notes. It can be considered as a grammar of musical phrases.

Each level is described with a set of features as follows:

- Note: attack type, pitch, string, finger, vibrato, nominal duration, tempo deviation (ritardando, rubato, etc.) dynamic and context (phrase, and gesture where it belongs to).
- Gesture: first note bow direction, notes, bow stroke ID. It can contain subgestures. There is a gesture ID, identifying the bow stroke type.
- Phrase: gestures, expressivity indications.

This representation is very near to physical controls, and thus, facilitates the matching between both.

3.1.2 Physical actions description

Most of the physical control descriptors are very similar to those of the score, and thus, they can be derived from the score more easily than the spectral descriptors.

Physical actions are described in a low level with the measurements from the sensors. As for the spectral descriptors we can build physical control descriptors over those low level ones. This part is still pending, as the sensing system is still in a primary development stage.

- Low level: bow position, bow pressure, bow-bridge distance, bow velocity, bow acceleration, finger and string.
- High level: still to define, to give an example, intensity of attack, discretized bow position (tip, frog, middle), bow force increase, and so on.

Figure 3.1: Score Description

In fig. 3.2, we can see an schema of the representation of the performance as curves of physical controls (that is, control trajectories or gestures), together with the waveshape as visual help.

3.1.3 Spectral description

Sound recordings are spectrally analyzed using SMS technique ([56]), then segmented and finally labeled with standard spectral features. Phrases are segmented into notes, and the notes into attack-sustain-release, semiautomatically. See fig. 3.3.

Spectral representation as slowly varying pitch and amplitude of each harmonic, together with the noise, as in [30], seems to be quite appropriate. See section 3.3 for further description of this technique.

Spectral descriptors

Standard features are extracted from the spectral analysis. See [37] for a summary of the main spectral descriptors. We find useful the followings:

- Note attack descriptors: we use log attack time that gives an idea of the pre-Helmholtz transient time (the duration of the attack) and temporal increase, the time until it reaches the sustain.
- Note transition descriptors: A descriptor that gives the degree of legato, as described in [31], could be useful.

Figure 3.2: Physical description

- Energy descriptors: total energy, harmonic energy, and noise energy in Bark Bands.
- Spectral shape descriptors: spectral moments (centroid, spread, skewness, and kurtosis), spectral slope, roll-off and MFCC's.

Figure 3.3: Sound Description

3.2 Performance actions measurement

Sound in a performance is controlled through actions made by the musician. Knowledge about the available controls and their effect on the sound is of great interest to build our model.

It is, thus, necessary to identify and measure those controls and analyze its influence on the sound.

Two types of measurements were carried out: Qualitative and Quantitative. Qualitative measurements depend on the subjective judgement of the player. Quantitative measurements are made with sensors that provide accurate values for each of the controls. Both approaches give interesting results and we can contrast the results of one with each other. The qualitative analysis consists of the timbre space analysis, carried out by sweeping and combining the control parameters in the playable range. The quantitative tests consist of analysis of performance gestures as well as timbre analysis as with the qualitative approach.

3.2.1 Violin physical controls

As stated in section 2.3.2, the available controls when performing with a violin are: bow position, velocity and acceleration, bow-bridge distance, bow force, bow tilt, bow hair width, rosin, string being played, vibrato and finger position on the string being played.

From all of them we find in the literature that the most relevant ones are bow position, bow-bridge distance, and bow force. We will focus our experiments on these three main parameters.

The objective is to understand how physical parameters are related to spectral descriptors. Not the whole timbre space produced by the combination of those parameters is of interest for us: only the sounds in the “Helmholz motion” regime (see section 2.2.3), and even a narrower subspace, formed by the possible sounds in normal performance conditions.

3.2.2 Qualitative analysis of violin physical controls

In this section we present the results of the analysis of the influence of different physical controls in the sound of the violin. The analysis will let us improve the synthesis quality by controlling those physical parameters.

Accurate measurements of the physical parameters have to be done, but as a first step until the availability of a developed sensing system, we will also make use of qualitative measurements.

The main controls to be analyzed are bow-bridge distance, bow position and bow force.

Setup for the measurements-methodology

The values of the control parameters are discretized into subjective intervals:

- bow-bridge distance into: bridge, middle and fingerboard.
- bow force into: soft, medium and hard.
- bow velocity into: slow, normal, fast.

A violinist is asked to play repeatedly a note several times all with the same fixed control parameters, while being recorded with a microphone. From the recordings the sustain of each note is extracted and analyzed, and an average spectrum is obtained and labeled with those fixed parameters. This process is repeated modifying one of the parameters while maintaining constant the rest, until we get a combination of all the different values of the parameters (In our case, three values each of the three parameters, makes twenty seven combinations). This way we obtain a n-dimensional timbre space of averaged spectra, where n is the number of parameters. All the process is also tracked with a video camera. The information in the video camera can be useful in order to contrast the validity of parameters such as bow velocity and bow-bridge position.

This is very useful for the synthesis stage as will be showed in section 3.3.2. For each point of that discrete timbre space, we store its corresponding spectrum envelope, instead of the whole spectrum, as if the timbre could be considered as an equalization of the sound. During the synthesis stage, if one sample from the database, needs to be transformed from one point in the space into another, the sample is convolved with a filter corresponding to the difference (in dB) of the spectra envelopes of the points.

Spectrum: Analysis and Representation

The aim of the analysis of the spectrum is to find a suitable representation, that will let us compare different spectra and transform one into another.

The spectral analysis is based on SMS ([56]). Several standard sound descriptors (see [37] for a summary) were obtained from the average magnitude spectra, namely, spectral envelope, spectral peaks, harmonic peaks, energy, harmonic energy, residual energy, spectral moments (centroid, spread, skewness, kurtosis) spectral slope, spectral roll-off, perceptual features (loudness, sharpness), MFCC coefficients and LPC coefficients. All the implementations were done in MATLAB.

Among all the descriptors previously enumerated, most of them have little interest concerning synthesis. They are more appropriate for a classification and recognition task (the inverse process), so they will not be presented here. We will concentrate on the descriptors that are relevant for the synthesis, that is, the ones that describe the spectral envelope (magnitude

spectrum, spectral peaks, spectrum envelope, LPC and MFCC coefficients). Manipulation of spectral envelopes can be done in all the previous representations as described in [51]. The most direct way is by interpolation of spectra with the disadvantage of having to keep it all in memory and to interpolate each of the points. We chose a spectrum envelope representation based on a smoothed envelope that is cheaper in memory use and faster to process as will be described in section 3.3.2. We can see in fig. 3.4 the magnitude spectrum and its smoothed spectrum.

Figure 3.4: Spectrum and spectrum envelope

Results

Following, we show the influence in the spectrum of modifying each of the input controls. However, it is very difficult or even impossible to individually control each parameter in such a qualitative approach, as it is controlled by a human performer. For instance, the force required to maintain the string in the Helmholtz motion increases as the bow is closer to the bridge. These correlations and other problems such as subjectivity make this approach not accurate, but nevertheless, we obtained some interesting results, and are the basis for more precise measurements.

General There is a constant in all the average spectra in the analyzed timbre space, all of them have very clearly localized peaks, that correspond to the harmonics of the sound. These fact give us a cue when separating noise from harmonic content in the SMS analysis. We can extract up to 70-90 clear harmonics, depending on the specific timbre, that are more deviated from the ideal harmonic series, in the high frequency range. In fig.3.5, we can see the ideal harmonic position for the first 90 harmonics, represented

as vertical lines equally separated, and three different average spectra, corresponding to the three different bow-bridge positions: close to the bridge (upper spectrum), close to the fingerboard (lower spectrum), and intermediate position (middle spectrum). We can see how the spectral peaks in each of the average spectra coincide, and are slightly deviated from the ideal, specially in the high frequencies. We can also observe how the spectrum corresponding to the position closer to the bridge has more high harmonics.

Figure 3.5: Peaks and harmonics

Knowledge of the average relation among harmonics and their standard deviation, can be useful in order to automatically generate them from the pitch, avoiding the necessity of storing them, at least for sustained segments of the notes.

In equation 2.3 we see the harmonic relation for a simplified model of string. If we substitute the parameters with the values in table 3.1 (as found in [23]), the equation returns values corresponding to an almost ideal harmonic relation. We can see at the top of fig. 3.6 that the value of Bn^2 is of order 10^{-9} . This quantity (coefficient of inharmonicity) is summed added to 1 in the equation, so its value is almost irrelevant.

However, this is quite different from the analysis of real data. At the bottom of fig. 3.6 we can see the results of the analysis of harmonic relation for the 70 first harmonics. Each of the series in the figure (blue and green),

represent the harmonics of an average spectrum of recordings of sustains of bowed notes with pith G3. The blue ones are notes bowed in an intermediate position between bridge and fingerboard and the green ones are played closer to the bridge. As we can see there are almost no differences. The figure represents the harmonic deviation from the ideal relation ($f_i = if_0$). The deviation is calculated as $dev(i) = \frac{f_i}{if_0}$, $i = 1..70$ and f_i =frequency of harmonic number i . A totally harmonic sound would give $dev(i) = 1, \forall i$. Notice that the deviation values are of order 10^{-3} , also very small. This means that the violin sound during the sustain part of the notes can be considered as highly harmonic. The deviation was fitted with a 4th-degree polynomial with value $y = -2.5e - 009x^4 + 2.7e - 007x^3 - 9.4e - 006x^2 + 0.00011x + 1$

	E string	A string	D string	G string
F0 [Hz]	660	440	294	196
Diameter [mm]	0.249-0.264	0.452-0.701	0.671-0.914	0.790-0.833
Tension [N]	72.25-84.01	48.89-63.51	34.76-61.73	35.43-49.92
Weight [g/m]	0.381-0.443	0.579-0.752	0.924-1.641	2.115-2.799

Table 3.1: Properties of violin strings from [23]

Figure 3.6: Harmonic deviation from ideally harmonic

Bow-bridge distance Except for some explicit fragments “sul ponticello” or “sul tasto”, in the classic violin technique, the player uses a very small

range of distances to play from close to the bridge to close to the fingerboard.

Figure 3.7: Bow Bridge distance

As we can see in fig.3.7, in general the closer to the bridge, the more the energy, except for a zone between the 22th and 23th bark bands. This is possibly due to harmonic cancelation when bowing on their antinode. The sound level distance in dB increases with the frequency achieving a value of 9dB in the high frequencies. It means that the timbre of a note, played close to the bridge will sound more brilliant (with more high harmonics) than the same note played near the finger board.

Other influences on the timbre are clear if we look at figure 3.8. Over the 4KHz we observe that the peaks in the notes played near the bridge are much sharper. This means that near the bridge, more high harmonics of the string are obtained and so, the harmonic component is bigger in that region. This phenomenon is emphasized over the 7Khz, where the spectrum corresponding to the fingerboard is quite flat, whereas the spectrum corresponding to the bridge maintains its sharpness.

Bow velocity As established by the classic work by Helmholtz on string motion, the period of the string motion is determined by the frequency of the lowest mode of the string, and not by the bow velocity as could seem to be. Bow velocity is directly proportional to the excursion of the string, that is, to the force exerted by the string on the bridge, that is, proportional to the sound level. We can see it in fig. 3.9: the sound level difference is noticeable in all the range of frequencies.

Bow force According to the Helmholtz motion, the bow force does not influence the string vibrations, but as is familiar to violin players, increasing bow force, gives a perceptually more brilliant and louder tone. Bow

Figure 3.8: Bow Bridge distance. High frequencies

force enables boosting the higher partials, producing a more brilliant tone. The amplitude of the string vibration remains almost unaltered, but as the human auditory sense is more sensible to high frequencies, we perceive an increase in loudness. It is quite difficult to isolate and analyze the effect of bow force in a real performance, because there is a close correlation with other control parameters like bow bridge distance. The minimum bow force required to maintain the Helmholtz oscillation increases as the bow is approached to the bridge. So during a performance when the force increases, normally the player tends to bow the string closer to the bridge. This effect gives the impression that with more force, loudness is increased, but the loudness is more influenced by the bow bridge distance as by the force. We can see in the video recording how the performer tends to play closer to the fingerboard when exerting low force, to avoid whistling sounds if played near the bridge, and tends to play closer to the bridge, when exerting a higher force, avoiding raucous tones if played far from the bridge. These effects are described in Schelleng's diagram (fig. 2.6). We can see in fig. 3.10, the result of the analysis. We can see that the sound level is higher with higher force, and is boosted in the high frequencies.

Figure 3.9: Bow velocity

Figure 3.10: Bow force

3.2.3 Quantitative analysis of violin physical controls

In this section we present the results of the analysis of the influence of the physical controls in the sound. It is a quantitative analysis, because the physical controls are measured with sensors. Special thanks go for Enric Gaus who developed the sensing system and participated in the recording sessions.

The analysis was made with the aim of having first results and of identifying the main features and problems, as a basis from which to improve the sensing system.

The measures are made for two type of experiments: Timbre analysis as with the qualitative analysis (3.2.2), and gesture analysis based on the experiments in [5], [6].

Setup for the measurements

Two violinists were asked to play their own violin, with a FSR sensor attached to the bow, under the forefinger, and an infrared sensor mounted as showed in fig. 3.11. They were asked to play the proposed exercises, while being recorded with a video camera and a microphone in a recording studio.

The sensors are connected to a Doepfer “Pocket Electronic”, a voltage to MIDI converter, to convert the signal from analog to digital in a MIDI format, ready to be recorded as a MIDI track synchronously with the sound.

In the following, we describe the methodology used to measure the main control parameters: bow force, bow-bridge distance and bow position.

Figure 3.11: Sensor system

Bow force measurement Different concepts are referred in the literature as “bow force” or “bow pressure” as can be seen in section 2.3.5.

We measure the input force exerted by the player with the left-hand forefinger on the bow. We use a Flexiforce FSR sensor (fig.3.12) because of the simplicity of signal conditioning and mounting and its non-intrusivity. FSR sensors are also used in other systems to measure bow force ([47]), so we count with a reference to compare with.

Figure 3.12: FSR Flexiforce sensor. Resistivity and conductance

The FlexiForce is a FSR (force sensing resistor). When the force sensor is unloaded, its resistance is very high. When a force is applied to the sensor, this resistance decreases.

In fig. 3.12, the plot shows both the Force vs. resistance and Force vs. conductance ($1/R$). Note that the conductance curve is linear, and therefore useful in calibration.

The way to integrate the force sensor into our sensing system is to incorporate it into a force-to-voltage circuit.

Bow-Bridge distance To measure the bow-bridge distance we use a Sharp GP2D120 infrared sensor. This sensor takes a continuous distance

reading each 50 ms, and reports the distance as an analog voltage with a distance range of 4cm to 30cm. In our configuration, we need to detect the distance in an approximate range between 4 and 10 cm, just in the region where the sensor is more sensible (fig. 3.13).

Figure 3.13: Sharp GP2D120 infrared sensor mounted and Distance vs Voltage

Bow Acceleration, Velocity and Position We are considering whether to use accelerometers or magnetic field sensors, but for these first measuring tests they were still not used.

Nevertheless, a video camera was used during the tests to track the movement of the bow. It is very useful for manual labeling of the measurements. A lot of information can be extracted: bow direction, approximation to velocity and bow position. Video images can also be used to contrast and validate the data obtained with the sensors.

Performance exercises

For the timbre analysis, the violinists were asked to play long bows with the same note (G open string), modifying increasingly each of the controls (bow force, bow-bridge distance, bow velocity).

For the gesture analysis, they were asked to play G major scales with different note lengths and bow strokes. See section 2.3 for summary of the main bow strokes. And two extra exercises consisting on diminuendo and crescendo, and an expressivity experiment, where they were asked to play the same excerpt with two different moods.

Results

Here we present the results of the measurements of bow-bridge distance and bow force with the sensing system previously described. See figs. 3.14, 3.15, 3.16.

We can see in the figures how in each bow stroke, be up-bow or down-bow, *bow-bridge* distance increases in the middle of the bow, and has its lowest value at the tip and frog (notice that in the figures, bridge is at the top and fingerboard at the bottom, so low bow-bridge distance value means a high value in the figure). This fact is due more to the sensing system than to the way of playing of the violinist. The infrared sensor measures the distance to the first obstacle where the beam reflects. The violinist when bowing, tilts the bow and although the bow hair remains on the same distance, the bow stick distance changes.

For the *bow force*, we can clearly see in all the figures as a constant feature, that the violinist applies the lowest force when playing at the frog, and the highest when playing at the tip. We are more interested in the force exerted by the bow on the strings, but we are measuring the force applied with the forefinger. If we want to obtain the latter, we should calculate the correlation between force on the string and bow position and apply a correction to the curve. We could take in advantage this feature to obtain the bow position from it.

As an extra parameter we show *bow position*, that is not measured, but obtained from the score itself. Looking at the video we could approximate the position of the bow during the bow direction changes.

We will refer to these two features in the rest of the section as the “bias of the sensing system”

Timbre analysis. With the timbre analysis we expect to make a similar analysis as with the qualitative experiment (3.2.2) but more accurate. The first step is, though, to validate that the sensing system is working appropriately and try to improve its weaknesses. So, in the following we make a rough analysis of the measurements.

In fig. 3.14, we can see three figures representing a sequence of G3 notes. The upper figure shows the measurements of a bow-bridge distance sweep: the played is asked to play a sequences of long notes sweeping the range of playable bow-bridge distance, from close to the bridge to close to the fingerboard, and trying at the same time to maintain the other controls constant. We can notice the bias of the sensing system in the local variations of the curves, but in average, we see clearly that the position is changing towards the fingerboard. This average motion is represented in the figure as a liner interpolation curve. In the wave shape plot, we can see how the closer to the bridge, the higher the sound level.

In the middle figure(from fig. 3.14) is represented the bow force sweep:

as in the previous case, we asked the violinist to play the same long notes, but this time varying increasingly the bow force applied. In this case we can also notice the bias of the sensing system, as well as the average increase of bow force. We can also see, that the bow-bridge position is unconsciously decreased. As the player exerts more bow force, she tends to play closer to the bridge to avoid the “raucous” string motion regime (see ?? for motion regime description). We see, as confirmed by traditional acoustic studies, that bow force and bow-bridge are correlated. We can also observe that the bigger the force, the larger? the amplitude in the wave shape (more sound level).

In the lower figure (from fig. 3.14), bow velocity sweep is represented. The player was asked this time to play the same notes, varying decreasingly the duration of the bow stroke. The measures parameters are constant in average, and we can see in the wave shape, that the sound level rises together with the velocity.

Articulation analysis. The tests made consist on a G mayor scale played with three different articulations. The results are showed in fig. 3.15. The main differences com up in the measurement of bow force.

In the upper figure (from fig. 3.15), we see the result for legato: the player was asked to play a scale of long notes, tying groups of two notes. We can see in the bow force plot, that although the curve has the bias of the sensing system, it has small peaks representing the attack of each of the notes.

For the middle figure (from fig. 3.15), the player was asked to pay the same scale but this time the notes are played in *detaché*. We can see how the peaks are sharper that for the legato notes, and the bias of the sensing system is not so present, because the bow strokes are not so long.

For the lower figure (from fig. 3.15), the player was asked to play the same scale *staccato*. We can see hear that the bias of the sensors is not at all present, because the bow stroke only covers a little part of the bow length, and we can see the peaks corresponding to each of the notes.

Crescendo-Decrescendo The last test consist on playing a long note in two bows, with a crescendo followed by a decrescendo. The results are showed in fig. 3.16.

In the upper figure, the player is asked to play the long note, bowing down and up. Here we can not see clearly the variation in the control parameters, because the *forte* coincides with the bow position at the tip, just where the sensor gives higher values. If we had made a correction of the bias of the sensing system, we should be able to see a peak of force in the *forte*. A decrease of bow-bridge distance should also be noticed, and an increase of bow velocity is noticed in the video, but not measured.

In the lower figure, the violinist performs the same, but changing the bow directions: first up, then down. Here we can see how the bias of the bow force sensor is counteracted by the increase of force in the *forte*: The *forte* takes place in the frog of the bow, the place where the sensor gives lowest force value. In the figure we can see, though, a local peak.

Figure 3.14: Bow-bridge distance, bow force and bow velocity sweeps

Figure 3.15: Articulation analysis in scales

Figure 3.16: Crescendo-Decrescendo analysis

3.3 Sound rendering

In this section we present some tests with spectral transformations of samples. The database of gestures, does not contain all the possible gestures, but a selection of the most relevant ones. The aim of the transformations is to be able to modify the stored gestures in order to cover the whole performance space (fig. 3.17)

Figure 3.17: Gesture transformation

3.3.1 Synthesis example with SPPTools

SPPTools is a framework for analysis, transformation, concatenation and re-synthesis of samples based on SPP technique (Spectral Peak Scaling, [8])

The goal of this experiment is twofold. On one hand we want to demonstrate that it is possible to improve the result of the synthesis result, provided with a database of gestures instead of single notes, and making use of existing spectral techniques for the transformations (in this case SPP).

On the other hand, we want to compare the synthesis results using a first database of sounds recorded directly with a microphone, a second database with the same sounds but previously deconvolved from the impulse response of the violin sound box (see sections 2.2.5 and 3.4), and a third database composed by the same corpus, played with an electric violin that will be later convolved with the impulse response of a violin sound box. The idea of this comparison is to see whether the transformations are simpler and of higher quality in the case of deconvolved or electric signals or not, and if the sound quality of the re-synthesis of a sample without transformations is as good as in the case of a recording.

The database in all the cases consist of two recordings: a non-expressive (without vibrato) three octave scale (ascendent and descendent) of semiquaver notes played *detaché*, and the same scale for quaver notes.

The selection of samples and the decision of transformations to be done was made manually using the following selection policy:


```

/*
Description:
Beginning of Allegro from "Praeludium und Allegro", Kreisler
Not expressive.
Selection policy:
    Similar selection as with the electric violin score
*/

//fragment1: DE->BE
sample=eighth_scale.wav
begin= 4.577
end= 5.302
PitchTransposition (0, 0.8409) (0.4248, 0.8409) (0.4248, 1) (1, 1)
TimeStretch 0 1.494 0.4949 1.494 0.4949 0.9554 1 0.9554
Gain 1.4

//fragment2 DC->DC
sample=sixteenth_scale.wav
begin=4.526
end=4.938
TimeStretch 0.8252
Gain 1.4

//fragment3 BAGF->BAGF
sample=eighth_scale.wav
begin=8.147
end=9.546
TimeStretch 1.0463
Gain 1.4

//fragment4 DEFG-EFEF
sample=sixteenth_scale.wav
begin=1.396
end=2.217
PitchTransposition (0 1.123) (0.5062 1.123) (0.5062 0.8909) (0.7984 0.8909) (0.7984 0.96) (1 0.96)
TimeStretch 0 1.35 0.249 1.35 0.249 0.7783 0.5091 0.7783 0.5091 0.7521 0.7953 0.7521 0.7953
1.0384 1 1.0384

//fragment5 FaSolLaSi-SolLaSolLa
sample=sixteenth_scale.wav
begin=1.726
end=2.702
PitchTransposition 0 1.0594 0.284 1.0594 0.284 1.1224 0.4726 1.1224 0.4726 0.8908 1 0.8908
TimeStretch 0 0.9224 0.2822 0.9224 0.2822 0.7885 0.5016 0.7885 0.5016 0.8621 0.7704 0.8621
0.7704 0.6726 1 0.6726

//fragment6 SiDoReMi-SiSolFaMi
sample=sixteenth_scale.wav
begin=2.426
end=3.207
PitchTransposition 0 1 0.3273 1 0.3273 1.4983 0.5432 1.4983 0.5432 1.2599 0.7982 1.2599
0.7982 1 1 1
TimeStretch 0 0.9556 0.283 0.9556 0.283 0.7833 0.5487 0.7833 0.5487 0.8168 0.7904 0.8168
0.7904 1.1176 1 1.1176

```

Figure 3.19: SPPTools synthesis score

Figure 3.20: Synthesis score explanation

the synthesis, by changing the bow stroke of the first notes, as appear in the score.

The same improvement that we get concatenating gestures instead of single notes, can be extrapolated to a higher level by concatenating whole phrases instead of gestures. The problem is that is it impossible to have all possible phrases stored in the database. To solve this problem, a “sound driven” synthesis was made: The same excerpt was played by a violinist, recorded, and analyzed. From the analysis we retrieved some features (namely energy and note onset-offset), that were applied to the synthesis, obtaining a much natural result, that includes phrasing.

This experiment confirms that a gesture based synthesis using existing techniques will improve the quality of a synthesized performance, but it is also of great importance to have a phrasing model that has to substitute the recording in the “sound driven” test.

3.3.2 Timbre transformations

Timbre is very rich and variable in bowed string instruments. The main controls that affect timbre as stated in the literature and as seems to be when performing are bow-bridge distance, bow velocity and bow force. In section 3.2.2, a qualitative analysis of the main bowing parameters was made, and we saw how the spectrum (and thus, the timbre) changes when varying these controls. If we consider the variation of timbre as an equalization of the sound, we can easily characterize it and transform from one timbre into another. We can consider the timbre as a three dimensional space with the previous controls as axes. Each point of the space, can be characterized with the envelope of an average spectrum, obtained by averaging the spectra of several sustained segments of notes belonging to that point (see section 3.2.2). The timbre of a sound belonging to a specific point in the space could be transformed into any timbre in another coordinates, by convolution of the sound with the filter corresponding to the relation of the average spectrum envelopes of both points.

We can see in fig. 3.21 three curves, representing the difference among three average spectra envelopes, corresponding to three different points in the space with coordinates:

1. [close to the bridge, medium force, middle velocity]
2. [equally distanced between bridge and fingerboard, medium force, middle velocity]
3. [close to h fingerboard, medium force, middle velocity]

As the values for the 2 last axes are the same, in the figure we only indicate the first coordinate. The curves are normalized to the second point, so we can see the relation among the three spectra. If we have a fragment of sound with the coordinates of the first or third cases, and we want to transform the timbre to the timbre corresponding to the second case, we have to multiply the spectrum of the fragment(in dB) with the timbre relation.

All the calculations were made in MATLAB. The spectral envelope is obtained with the “filtfilt” function, that computes a running average filter of a signal in two phases, first in one direction, then in the reserved direction, so the result is the smoothed signal, without delay.

Results and conclusions

The hypothesis of considering the timbre as an equalization of the sound, seems appropriate. For the parameters bow-bridge distance and bow pressure, the transformation seem to work, but not for the bow velocity.

It seems a promising approach in order to modify the timbre, but still a lot of work and listening tests should be done to confirm its validity.

Figure 3.21: Spectrum Envelope relations

An improvement would be to represent each timbre as the envelope of the harmonics and the envelope of the noise separately. Notice also that the timbre is mainly appropriate for the sustained part of the sound. Although it seems to work also for the attacks, special care should be taken. Hard attacks are not possible in a position close to the fingerboard.

Apart from the cited controls, the string being played is also of great importance in the timbre, and should also be considered as other parameter in the timbre space.

3.3.3 Slowly and rapidly varying sound features

The idea of slowly and rapidly varying pitch and loudness is taken from [30]. There, the spectral representation of the samples, called RPLHN (residual pitch, loudness, and harmonics + noise), consists on the storage of only the rapid variations of the pitch and the frequency and amplitude of each harmonic, together with the noise. The slowly varying pitch and loudness is given by a MIDI stream of note-on pitch and note-on velocity. The rapidly varying pitch and loudness are the fluctuations that make the sound to be rich and real.

An experiment was made based on this idea. A musical phrase was recorded and analyzed using the harmonic+noise SMS technique([56]). Residual and harmonic part is separated. The harmonic part is represented as trajectories of Amplitudes and Frequencies for each of the harmonic and a pitch curve is obtained.

The pitch curve is then separated into slowly varying pitch and rapidly varying pitch. The slowly fluctuations can be obtained in several ways: low-pass filtering, smoothing the pitch curve, or segmenting the notes, and giving a unique value for the whole note segment. The rapidly varying fluctuations are the difference between the curve and the slowly varying ones. We will store in the database as pitch curve, only these rapid fluctuations, and the frequencies of the harmonics will consist on the variation respect this rapid pitch curve.

We can see in fig. 3.22, in upper figure, a plot of the pitch curve, and the quantization for the slowly varying pitch (MIDI pitch), consisting on a unique value for each note segment. In the figure below, we can see the difference between the whole curve and the slowly varying curve, that is, the rapid fluctuations.

This representation for the pitch and harmonic frequencies, is independent of the note pitch. A sequence of MIDI notes (that is, the slowly varying pitch) is given to a function in MATLAB, that uses the rapid fluctuations of the analyzed phrase, and returns a phrase that preserves the idiomatic musical structure (phrasing, note transitions, etc...) but with different note pitch.

As well as with the pitch, we could do the same with other features, such as amplitude.

Results and conclusions

This technique is very promising, because we can store the gestures independently of the pitch and as well as for the pitch it could be extrapolated to other features such as partial's amplitude. This makes easier the transformations and as each phrase can cover different combinations of pitch, the database becomes smaller.

Figure 3.22: Slow and rapid pitch variations

In order to be able to do it, a fine separation of the signal into harmonic and noise is necessary. Sometimes in the recordings, there are resonances from other strings or previous notes that appear in the residual. They should be taken into account in the separation as well as in the transformation.

3.3.4 Other transformations

Concatenations are a special type of transformation involving two samples. The tests that we made until now, were using the concatenations of the SPPTools framework. Smoothed transitions between the features of both samples is applied.

A feature that is of paramount importance is vibrato. Almost every note played with a violin in traditional music performance has vibrato. Concatenation and transformation and of notes with vibrato has to be feasible. In fig. 3.23 we can see the analysis of a note with vibrato. The upper plot shows the pitch of the note in frames, after applying SMS analysis. In the lower plot, we see the spectrum of two frames (frames number 54 and 64 of the SMS analysis, as showed) with different pitch. We can see that the pitch is different because of the harmonics (it is clearer in the high harmonics), and that the envelope of the spectra changes. There is not only a frequency modulation, but also amplitude modulation, involving a change in the timbre. We did not investigate in this direction, but it seems an advantage to

Figure 3.23: Vibrato Analysis

use the separated model of the violin (source and radiator), because of the complex resonances of the violin body. Another possibility could be to filter the frequency modulations with a spectral envelope with all the resonances.

3.4 Source-radiator separation

The separation of the system into source and resonator will play an important role in our system. It can be seen as a characteristic of physical models, as we considered them to be those that model the production of sound. We are, though, not using any mathematical formulae to model any acoustic phenomena, but a spectral model inspired on physical characteristics.

In the literature about violin acoustics ([13], [23]), we can see that the violin is mainly composed by 3 resonators : strings, bridge and acoustic box(body). The strings are excited and the vibration is transmitted to the body through the bridge. The performer controls the vibration of the strings, through the fingers and the bow. And the bridge and body act passively as a filter that modifies the obtained vibration.

We will separate the system into two parts, and model them independently: the first part, composed by the strings that can be considered as the exciter, the source or the controllable part, and the second part, composed by the bridge together with the body, that can be considered as the sound radiator or filter (see fig. 3.24).

Figure 3.24: Sound Source and Sound Radiator separation

Apart from the reasons stated before, with the separation we obtain theoretically a simpler signal without resonances that is much easier to transform, concatenate and synthesize with higher quality than the whole one.

To do the signal separation, we measured the response of the body and extracted the source using signal deconvolution. See section 2.2.5 for a broader discussion in signal separation.

Following we explain how to measure and model the body of the violin and how to obtain the source signal.

3.4.1 Measuring the frequency response of the body

Given that we assume that the body is almost passive and linear, it acts as a linear filter over the signal produced by the excitation between bow and string. To characterize the filter we should know its impulse response, that can be measured in several ways as seen in section 2.2.5

The selected approach for exciting the violin was by hitting the bridge. We did it by hitting with different objects: finger, nail, metallic hammer, rubber hammer, force hammer (see fig. 3.24) and we measured the impulse response with a microphone and with laser. The setup and results for each measurement are explained next.

Hitting with different objects and recording with microphone

In this experiment the violin was hit in different positions of the bridge, with different objects ranging from finger, nail, metallic hammer, rubber hammer, with the strings muted and open. The response was obtained with a microphone.

There is a big difference among the impulse responses obtained depending on the position where it is excited, on the type of object used for the excitation, on the strings if they were muted or not, and on the violin, if it was hold or not. We can compare the results with figures appearing in the literature such as the one in fig. 2.9. We can observe that in all the figures, the most important modes in the low frequencies (until 1kHz) appear: A0 resonance around 270Hz, P1 between 400 and 500 Hz, P2 between 500 and 600 Hz:

Material of hitting object. In fig. 3.25 we can see the different responses for a metal hammer, a plastic hammer, and a nail. It seems that the plastic hammer gives a very bad response for high frequencies, due certainly to the low frequency content of the excitation. The nail gives a quite good response and the metal hammer gives a response with a lot of peaks and valleys.

Muted or open strings Although all strings resonate while playing, we are interested in the impulse response of the sounding box, not of the sounding box and the strings, so it is expected to have better results with muted strings. The time response with open strings is much longer (around 250ms) than the one with muted strings (around 60ms). The results of the convolution are much better with the response with muted strings as expected, except for the convolution with an electric violin signal, that is much reacher if the response was taken with open strings.

Excitation position. In fig. 3.26 we can see the difference of the responses by hitting the bridge with the nail on the E-side and on the G-side. It

Figure 3.25: Impulse Response for different materials

seems better the response for the G-side of the bridge. This is quite sensible because of the physical configuration of the violin and bridge, that as can be seen in fig. 3.27 has more mobility in the G-side.

Violin hold for playing In fig. 3.28, we can see the response of the violin to an impulse excitation with a metal hammer. The upper figure shows the response for the violin when it is free, and the bottom figure shows the response when the violin is hold in the position of playing. We can see how the modes are not so clear, because of the contact. But we still see clearly the main modes of the violin.

Hitting with force hammer and measuring mobility with laser

These measurements were made in the laboratories of University “La Salle” in Barcelona, with the help of Enric Gaus and Sergi Soler.

In this experiment the violin bridge was struck laterally in the G-side with a force-hammer, and the mobility of the body measured in three points with laser (fig. 3.29)

Figure 3.26: E-side vs G-side Impulse Response

Figure 3.27: Violin Section

The average of the mobility at the three points is as showed in fig. 3.30. The main difference with the previous measurements is that the air resonance is much weaker, because we are measuring the mobility and not sound pressure. In the upper figure we can see the resonances in a similar scale to the previous measurements for comparison, and in the lower plot we can see a wider range of the frequency response.

3.4.2 Source signal

The source signal is obtained from the deconvolution of the impulse response of the violin body from the whole signal. The deconvolution is made by convolution with an inverse impulse response of the sound box, as explained in section 2.2.5. The inverse impulse response is calculated with an implemen-

Figure 3.28: Hold vs not Hold Impulse Response

tation of a least-squares algorithm that appears in [35] developed by the authors of [15].

In fig. 3.31 we can see at the top, the impulse response of the sound box, followed by the inverse impulse response. Then we see the result of the convolution of impulse response and the inverse impulse response in time and frequency domains. As expected, it is a nearly delta function with a flat spectrum.

Figure 3.29: Excitation with force hammer and measurement of mobility with a laser. Picture taken from [18]

Figure 3.30: Mobility of the sound box measured with laser

Figure 3.31: Impulse Response and Inverse Filter

Chapter 4

Proposed Approach and Future Work

In this chapter we compile all the ideas already presented along the work, and put them together in the form of a new approach for a synthesizer for bowed string instruments, although the synthesizer architecture may also serve to render other types of instruments.

As we told in section 2.1.3, the idea is to define a starting point with a model based on recordings or Cases, and go towards a more parametrical model through analysis of data and sound transformations (see fig. 2.2). The starting point will be described next, and the development of the system towards a more parametric model, will be the guideline for future work.

4.1 System Overview

In this section we will give an overview of the proposed system, presenting the main blocks, as showed in fig. 4.1

The input to the system is a score. The first main block is *Gesture Generation*. From the incoming score, the corresponding sequence of gestures has to be generated.

The second block is *Gesture Selection*, consisting in the database and a selection algorithm. In this stage, the most similar stored gesture to the target gesture is selected, and sent to the rendering stage.

The third building block is *Sound Rendering*. This block receives as input the target gesture and the selected gesture available in the database. It is responsible for transforming the selected gesture into the target gesture, for concatenating the incoming gestures, and for outputting the synthesized sound.

Figure 4.1: System Overview

4.2 Database

The database consists of a corpus of musical phrases containing performance gestures. As showed in fig.4.1, we can see that from all possible sounds that can be produced by the instrument, we are only interested in the musically relevant ones, and from these we have only a subset in the database, represented as trajectories in the figure. The rest of the musically relevant sound space should be covered by transformations of the stored gestures. The definition of the corpus of gestures in the database is crucial for the synthesis quality. An identification of the most relevant performance gestures, and the analysis of the extent of the transformations is necessary.

Our database will have some novelties regarding other approaches, that justify the main contributions of this research to synthesis models:

- **It is gesture centered:** The stored data consists of musical phrases that contain gestures covering most of the gesture space. Notes are used in most of the synthesizers as the unit from which a performance can be assembled, but during a musical performance, notes can not be considered as isolated elements that can be separated. We consider gestures as repeated patterns of performance control trajectories that produce sounds corresponding to groups of notes that are played “together”. When concatenating these groups of notes, we will have the same problem as when concatenating two notes, but in a much lower degree, so it is important to consider a phrasing model when

concatenating them in the rendering stage.

Most of the expression and note grouping in bowed string instruments is controlled by the bow. We will concentrate on bowing articulation in order to identify the gestures and build the corpus of the database.

- **Three types of data information will be stored:** sound, physical controls and score. This way we can have a correspondence between the different domains of performance information. While the performance is recorded, some bowing parameters are measured and everything is stored together with the corresponding score.
- **The sound representation,** will not consist of analyzed recordings made with a microphone, but of the source signal obtained by source-radiator signal separation. (see sections 2.2.5 and 3.4)

4.2.1 Database selection

This block will be responsible for selecting the gesture or concatenation of gestures that is most similar to a desired gesture.

The input is a gesture from the musical relevant gesture space (see fig. 4.1), and the output is the most similar gesture (or concatenation of gestures) available in the database. As the database contains information about physical controls, sound, and score, the input may be any of those representations or a combination of them, and the output would be a translation of one representation into another.

We will mainly focus on the translation from score to sound going through physical actions, so in this case the input to this block will consist of a mixture of the three representations (sound, control, and score) coming from the *Gesture Generation* block, and the output will be the sound representation that will be sent to the *Sound Rendering* block. Nevertheless several scenarios of input-outputs are possible for different types of applications: In the case of sound as input and score as output, we are dealing with transcription. If the input to the synthesizer are physical actions, we could control the synthesis with a violin.

We could see the problem of finding a representation of any gesture from a known set of examples (the database) as a Case Base Reasoning system.

4.3 Gesture Generation

This block together with the database selection block are the equivalent of the performer as shown in the general performance loop (fig. 1.1). They constitute the “performer model”. It is responsible of transforming symbolic musical information (that is, a score), into a gesture in form of physical and/or spectral representations.

4.3.1 From Score to Physical and Spectral domains

Physical models generally model the translation from physical actions into sound, and spectral models generally map score representations to spectral representations of the sound directly. Nevertheless, the normal flow of musical information in a real performance is from score to physical actions, and then to sound (see fig. 1.1).

The gesture generated in this block will be used to retrieve the most similar one in the database, and to identify the transformations to be done. The additional representation of the data also as physical controls, gives a lot of gestural information that will be of great help in the gesture selection stage and will provide cues about the necessary transformations to be done.

Moreover, it seems that the transformation from score to physical controls, as it happens in the real performance, is easier to model: There is a lot of implicit and explicit information in a score, normally related more with physical controls than with spectral ones. It is the case of ties, bow strokes, fingering, bow direction, etc. Apart from that, we hope that the analysis of the performance control trajectories will give us extra useful information regarding the mapping.

The tandem *gesture generation* and *database knowledge* can be seen as a model with two levels of detail as in [30]. *Gesture generation* will generate slowly varying controls, and the database will provide the rapid varying controls. Furthermore, the database will provide those rapid varying details in the sound domain.

4.4 Sound Rendering

This stage makes use of both the generated gesture and the gesture or gestures retrieved from the database. The aim is to make the necessary transformations and concatenations to the selected gestures in order to transform them into a meaningful musical phrase. In the concatenation of the gestures we must take special care to be consistent with respect to physical descriptors (bow position, fingering, etc.) and spectral descriptors (timbre, dynamics, spectral shape, etc.). Furthermore, we have to be aware of the overall phrasing, so a model of phrasing may be of great help.

4.4.1 Transformations

This block works with information converted into the sonic domain, in a spectral representation. It is basically the spectral model part of the system.

The overall success of the synthesis will depend on the database corpus and on the quality of the transformations and concatenations. Using both we should be able to cover the whole musical relevant space (fig. 4.1).

The main transformations will consist of time stretch/pitch shift, slowly varying + rapidly varying features, concatenations, timbre transformations and vibrato as explained in section 3.3.

4.4.2 Source-Radiator Separation

The signal of the instrument is divided into two parts: the part that generates the sound (source) and the part that filters the source and radiates the sound. As seen in sections 2.2.5 and 3.4, the source is composed by both the string and the bow interacting, and represents the dynamic and non-linear part of the system. And the radiator is composed by the sound board and the air cavity, that is almost a static and linear. This separation is related to the production of sound and thus, it can be considered as a characteristic of physical models.

Both parts can be separately modeled and at the sound rendering stage put again together. The radiator, can be considered a quasi-linear system, and thus it can be modeled as a linear filter, and the source can be spectrally modeled.

But why this separation if we must model the source signal the same way without separation? The objective is twofold: On one hand we believe that we will obtain a cleaner signal without the reverberation produced by the soundboard, that is easier to transform and concatenate, and on the other hand the recordings may be simplified, because we could avoid the problems of differently sounding instrument bodies and sound projection directionality.

With the separation, extra controls for the resonator could also be provided, although they are not strictly necessary to get a natural sound. Examples of such controls could be:

- Sound projection direction: The sound of the violin is projected into the air, and it is slightly different for each direction in the space.
- Parameters of the resonant body: dimensions, frequency response, etc.

Conclusion

In this work, we identified the main problems in synthesis of musical performances for the case of sustained excitation instruments, and we presented a new synthesis approach that is based on performance gestures, and that can be considered a hybrid system between spectral and physical models, because it tries to take advantage of characteristics from both approaches.

We demonstrated that with the existing techniques, it is possible to improve existing techniques of musical performances, by focusing on gestures. Provided with a good database of musical phrases containing previously identified gestures, and a set of high quality spectral transformations, we can cover all the performance sound space.

Furthermore, we proposed a way of measuring actions during a performance, based on the main reported contributions in the field, that will provide us with gestural information for building the performer model.

A set of spectral transformations was also presented, that will be of great help to cover a larger performance sound space, and to reduce the database of analyzed samples.

The idea of separating the sound signal of the violin into source signal, and radiator signal is introduced and some solutions are discussed.

Finally, it was proposed the architecture of a synthesizer that considers all the previous characteristics, and conforms a basis from which a future work guideline towards a more parametric model is given.

The main contributions that we intend to make in the future are in the performance model by improving the measurements and analysis of performance actions, in the spectral transformations and in the separation of the sound source and the sound radiator.

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